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IN SILICO DOCKING ANALYSIS OF PHYTOCOMPOUNDS FROM *Anisopus manii* N.E.BR. LEAF FOR POTENTIAL ANTIDIABETIC APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Several α -glucosidase inhibitors, such as acarbose, voglibose, and miglitol, have been extensively reported in the literature and are commonly employed to manage postprandial blood glucose levels. Nonetheless, the prolonged use of these drugs is often associated with side effects, including diarrhea, abdominal discomfort, and other gastrointestinal complications. As a result, there is a pressing need to discover new natural compounds with strong α -glucosidase inhibitory properties and minimal adverse effects. This research seeks to explore and identify novel α -glucosidase inhibitors from the extract of *Anisopus manii* N.E.Br., aiming to develop effective treatments for type II diabetes mellitus. *Anisopus manii* was extracted, the active components were identified using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometric (GC-MS) technique, and the compounds were docked with Autodock 4.0 program. The results of the docking studies of the identified phyto molecules with α -glucosidase enzyme (2CAG) revealed that these compounds possessed distinct affinities with the α -glucosidase enzyme, ranging from -6.05 kcal/mol (1-Allyl-cyclohexane-1,2-diol with CID7710) to -5.54 kcal/mol (CID_536559). The results, however, showed that the compound with CID_7710 had the best binding energy of -6.05 kcal/mol and formed a hydrogen bond with Arg51 and Arg54. Similarly, the phyto compound with CID_138243 possesses the binding affinity of -5.69 kcal/mol and forms a hydrogen bond with Arg51, Ser348, and interacts with a peptide of α -glucosidase through electrostatic interaction with Ser348. However, compound with CID_536995 had a minimum binding energy of -5.54 kcal/mol. The knowledge gained from this work can be further used in experimental studies to design α -glucosidase inhibitors involved in the treatment of diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: *Anisopus manii*; Diabetes Mellitus; α -Glucosidase; Molecular Docking

INTRODUCTION

The plant *Anisopus manii* is a perennial herbaceous shrub in the subfamily *Asclepiadoideae* of the family *Apocynaceae* commonly referred to as the dogbane family [1]. The flowering species grows in the tropical environments of central Africa and is renowned in traditional Nigerian medicine for treating sexual impotence, the common cold, diarrhea, and most notably, its potent hypoglycemic effect. Recent research has been conducted, looking into the species' potential anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antimicrobial, and antioxidant bioactivities and mechanisms of action [2].

Diabetes mellitus is a life-threatening and chronic metabolic turmoil, it is deemed one of the most common and grave diseases of the 21st century. This illness is caused by deficient insulin secretion and marked by hyperglycemia [3]. High levels of glucose in blood lead to some acute problems to human organs such as nerves, kidneys, heart, and eyes [4].

α -Glucosidase is an enzyme located in the epithelium of the small intestine, and due to its ability to transform the hydrolysis of disaccharides and polysaccharides into glucose [5]. Various α -glucosidase inhibitors such as acarbose, voglibose, and miglitol have been reported in the literature and are adopted to decrease the postprandial blood glucose levels [6,7]. Unfortunately, these drugs have many side effects such as diarrhea, abdominal pain and other gastrointestinal disorders in chronic therapy [8]. As a result, the discovery of new agents with high α -glucosidase inhibitory activity and weak side effects became of great importance. The present study was carried out to identify novel inhibitors of alpha glucosidase from extract of *Anisopus manii* for the treatment of type II diabetes mellitus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

The chemicals and reagents (Alloxan, methanol, distilled water, NaOH, FeCl₂, NaCO₃, Chloroform, Ciocalten's reagent and H₂SO₄) used in the research were purchased from BDH Chemicals Ltd. Poole, England and are of analytical grade.

Sample Collection and Identification

Fresh leaf sample of *Anisopus manii* was collected from Maiduguri, Borno State and identified by a Botanist from the Department of Biological Science, and voucher sample (Vet252B25) was deposited at the Veterinary Pharmacology Laboratory Herbarium, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.

Methanol Extract Preparation

The *Anisopus manii* sample was shed-dried and ground to a powdered form using a mortar and pestle. Then it was extracted by maceration extraction method with methanol and distilled water at a ratio of 70:30. The extract was evaporated to dryness in a silver tray, and the sample was collected in a plastic container and kept in a refrigerator before usage.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of Methanol Leaf Extract of *Anisopus manii*

The phytochemical analysis of the methanol leaves extract of *Anisopus manii* was carried out using the methods of [9].

Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀)

The acute toxicity study of the methanol leaves extract of *Anisopus manii* was conducted using the method as described by Lorke [10]. The extract of the plant was administered orally using sterile orogastric tubes and the following formula was used to calculate the LD₅₀:

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{a * b}$$

Where a = Highest dose that gave no mortality and

b = Lowest dose that produces mortality

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis

The phytocompounds of the methanol leaf extract of *Anisopus manii* were identified using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). The 7890A gas chromatograph system (Agilent 19091-433HP, USA) and mass spectrophotometer were used to perform the GC-MS analysis. The system was equipped with an HP-5 MS fused silica column (5% phenyl methyl siloxane 30.0m 250 m, film thickness 0.25 m), which was interfaced with a 5675C Inert MSD with Triple-Axis detector. As the carrier gas, helium gas was adjusted to a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. Other GC-MS conditions include a 1 l injector in split mode with a split ratio of 1:50 and an injection temperature of 300 °C. Ion source temperature is 250 °C, interface temperature is 300 °C, pressure is 16.2 psi, and out time is 1.8 mm. The column temperature increased from 36 °C to 150 °V at a rate of 4 °C/min after starting at 36 °C for 5 minutes. The temperature was raised to 250⁰. The sample is injected into the GC-MS system, where compounds are separated according to their volatility and polarity. The mass spectrometer then ionizes these compounds and determines their

mass-to-charge (m/z) ratios, generating fragmentation patterns. These patterns are compared against spectral database (NIST) to identify possible compounds.

Molecular Docking Analysis

The identified compounds are matched to reference spectra, and their molecular formula and fragmentation patterns help infer their structural characteristics. To further analyze the identified compounds, their names, CAS numbers, or molecular formulas are searched in the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). The corresponding PubChem Compound Identifier (CID) is retrieved, providing comprehensive details on molecular structure, chemical properties, and biological activities. The GC-MS-identified compounds are then converted into PDB format using Open Babel.

The three-dimensional (3-D) structures of the α -glucosidase enzyme and the ligands (phytochemicals) used in this research were obtained from Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics (RCSB) PDB database and Pubchem, respectively. The target protein (receptor) obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) undergoes preparation by removing water molecules and adding hydrogen atoms. Using AutoDockTools (ADT), a grid box is placed around the active site of the receptor to define the docking area. Both the receptor and ligands are converted to PDBQT format, ensuring torsional flexibility in the ligands.

The physicochemical and pharmacokinetic properties of the bioactive compounds of *Anisopus maniii* were conducted using data warrior tool, whereas the docking studies were performed with the help of Autodock 4.0 program. Docking simulations are conducted using AutoDock Vina, which predicts the optimal binding conformations based on binding affinity (ΔG in kcal/mol). Multiple binding poses are generated and ranked based on docking scores. The best binding pose is visualized in PyMOL, highlighting key interactions such as hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic contacts. Finally, docking scores and interaction profiles are analyzed to evaluate the binding efficiency of the compounds [11,12].

RESULTS

Table 1: Phytochemical Constituents of Methanol Leaf extract of *Anisopus maniii*

Phytoconstituents	Result
Alkaloids	+
Tannins	+
Terpenes	+
Flavonoids	+
Steroids	+
Phenols	+

Key: (+) indicate the presence of phytochemicals

Acute Toxicity Studies (LD₅₀)

Table 2: Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) Study of the Methanol leaf Extract of *Anisopus maniii*

Group	Dose (mg/kg body weight)	Number of deaths	Behavior
Phase 1	10	0/3	Normal
	100	0/3	Normal
	1000	0/3	Normal
Control	0	0/3	Normal
Phase 2	1600	0/1	Hair erection
	2900	0/1	Body shivering
	5000	0/1	Slow movement

GC-MS Analysis

Table 3: Properties of Compounds Isolated from Methanol Extract of *Anisopus maniii*

Pubchem ID	Compound	Formular	M/W	Retention time	Peaks
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21242	Formaldehyde,(2-butenyl) methylhydrazone	C ₆ H ₁₂ N ₂	112	2.753	1
7710	1-Allyl-cyclohexane-1,2-diol	C ₉ H ₁₆ O ₂	156	2.753	1
5463762	Cyclooctaneacetic acid, 2-oxo-	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₃	184	2.753	1
10345	Bicyclo[2.2.1]hept-2-en-7-ol	C ₇ H ₁₀ O	110	3.937	2
9240	1-Azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane, 4-methyl	C ₈ H ₁₅ N	125	3.937	2
10038543	4-(o-Tolyl)-3,4-dihydro-1H-1,4-benzodiazepine-2,5-dione	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	266	3.937	2
24835	4-Acetoxy-3-methoxystyrene	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₃	192	4.355	3
8797	Ethanone, 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl phenyl)- Formula: C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ MW: 150 Exact Mass: 150	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂	150	4.355	3
83346	4(1H)-Pyrimidinone, 6-methyl	C ₅ H ₆ N ₂ O	110	4.59	4
11271	1-Pentanol, 4-methyl-2-methylene	C ₇ H ₁₄ O	114	5.66	6
11592	Hexane, 2,5-dimethyl	C ₈ H ₁₈	114	5.66	6
14671060	Tetramethylpentadecan-3-one	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O	282	6.661	7
75719	Methyl 11-oxo-9-undecenoate	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₃	212	6.781	8
8031	meso-2,5-Dimethyl-3,4-hexanediol	C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₂	146	7.016	9
f118290	D-Fructose, 3-O-methyl-Formula: C ₇ H ₁₄ O ₆ MW: 194 Exact Mass: 194.0	C ₇ H ₁₄ O ₆	194	7.016	9
8181	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	270	8.904	10
110919	2-Propanesulfinic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester	C ₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ S	136	9.207	11
8180	Undecanoic acid	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ O ₂	186	9.35	12
145386	3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2 hexadecen-1-ol	C ₂₂ H ₄₀ O	296	10.689	15
8201	Methyl stearate	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O ₂	298	10.769	16
18686	Name: 1-Allyl-cyclohexane-1,2-diol	C ₉ H ₁₆ O ₂	156	11.307	18
62092	-2-Methyl-2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)pentanone-4	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂	192	12.56	19
8814	Phenol, 4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	206	15.061	20
8814	Phenol, 4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	206	15.496	21

Physicochemical Analysis

All the compounds obtained from GC-MS analysis were further filtered for physicochemical properties (molecular ≤ 500 Da, number of hydrogen bond acceptor ≤ 10, number of hydrogen bond donor ≤ 5, logp ≤ 5, logs ≤ 5 and Druglikeness). All the compounds had desirable physicochemical properties.

Table 3: Physicochemical Properties of the Compounds Isolated from Methanol Leaf Extract of *Anisopus maniii*.

S/N	PubChem ID	Molecular weight (≤500)	Number of HBA (≤10)	Number of HBD (≤5)	MolLogP (≤5)	Druglikeness
1	CID_5364995	112.175	2	0	1.0247	-0.39093
2	CID_7710	156.224	2	0	2.1221	-15.536
3	CID_138243	184.234	3	0	1.182	-9.5436
4	CID_536995	184.234	3	1	1.9786	-7.9955
5	CID_40898	110.155	1	1	0.8279	-1.2425
7	CID_577861	266.299	4	1	2.0243	3.6405
8	CID_591597	192.213	3	0	2.2792	-4.4307
9	CID_31217	150.176	2	0	1.2054	-7.1994
10	CID_74877153	196.293	3	2	1.3659	-0.723
11	CID_545223	114.187	1	1	2.0529	-7.1783
12	CID_582854	290.594	2	0	5.8424	-58.261

13	CID_180973	282.510	1	0	6.7046	-9.7863
14	CID_534673	212.288	3	0	2.8272	-30.386
15	CID_552199	146.229	2	2	1.1878	-1.6676
16	CID_164619	194.182	6	5	-2.6327	-3.7296
17	CID_8181	270.455	2	0	6.4904	-35.364
18	CID_543690	136.214	2	0	1.0517	-6.7719
19	CID_8180	186.294	2	1	3.7905	-25.216
20	CID_5280435	296.537	1	1	7.4212	-3.7661
21	CID_8201	298.509	2	0	7.3992	-35.364
22	CID_5365049	156.224	2	0	2.5549	-5.0308
23	CID_61052	192.257	2	0	2.8858	-4.5021
24	CID_8814	206.328	1	1	4.5887	-5.8012
25	CID_22644018	324.506	1	1	6.486	-5.8012

Pharmacokinetic Properties

Table 4: Pharmacokinetic Properties of the Compounds Isolated from Methanol Leaf Extract of *Anisopus maniii*

S/no.	Compound name	BBB	CYP2D6 inhibitor	GIA	Mutagens	Tumorigens	Reproducibility	Irritant
1	CID_5364995	+	Non-inhibitor	+	Low	None	None	None
2	CID-7710	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	Low
3	CID_138243	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	High
4	CID_536995	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	None
5	CID_40898	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	None
6		+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	None
7	CID_577861	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	None
9	CID_31217	+	Non-inhibitor	+	High	High	High	High
10	CID_74877153	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	none
11	CID_545223	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	Low	Low
12	CID_582854	+	Inhibitor	+	None	None	None	High

13	CID_180973	-	Non-inhibitor	-	None	None	None	none
14	CID_534673	+	Non-inhibitor	-	Low	high	None	low
15	CID_552199	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	none
16	CID_164619	-	Non-inhibitor	-	None	None	None	none
17	CID_8181	+	Non-inhibitor	-	None	None	None	none
18	CID_543690	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	none
19	CID_8180	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	high
20	CID_5280435	-	Non-inhibitor	-	None	None	None	none
21	CID_8201	+	Non-inhibitor	-	None	None	None	none
22	CID_5365049	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	high
23	CID_61052	+	Non-inhibitor	+	None	None	None	high
24	CID_8814	+	Inhibitor	+	None	High	High	high
25	CID_22644018	-	Inhibitor	-	None	None	None	low

Docking Score

Table 5: Docking Scores and Residues involved in H-Bond Formation

S/No.	Compound ID	Docking score	Residues involve in H-Bonds	Distance
2	CID7710	-6.05kcal/mol	Arg51 Arg54 Arg54	2.97 3.22 3.01
3	CID_138243	-5.69 kcal/mol	Arg51 Ser348	3.25 3.05
4	CID_536995	-5.66 kcal/mol	Asp346 Arg54 Arg54	3.68 2.63 2.96
23	CID_61052	-5.54	Arg51 Thr295	2.86 2.71

a. (CID_7710)

b. CID_61052

c. CID_536995

c. CID_61052

Fig. 1: Ligand Interactions of α -glucosidase enzyme with: (a) compound 2 (CID_7710); (b) compound 3 (CID_138243); (c) compound 4 (CID_536995); and (d) compound 23 (CID_61052).

DISCUSSION

Phytochemicals are compounds with biological action that are mostly produced by plants. Plants are the primary source of different active compounds used in medicinal products. They show pharmacological properties that can be used to treat fungal and bacterial infections as well as degenerative conditions like cancer and diabetes that are chronic. The phytochemical screening of the methanol leaf extract of *Anisopus maniii* revealed the presence of

alkaloids, tannins, terpenoids, flavonoids, steroids, and phenols. This result corresponds to the findings of Sani *et al.* [13], which showed that *Anisopus maniii* extract is a good source of phytochemicals. The acute toxicity study of the methanol leaf extract of *Anisopus maniii* revealed no mortality or signs of toxicity at various doses, up to a maximum dose of 5000 mg/kg body weight. This suggests that the extract is relatively safe for oral consumption, supporting its traditional use in herbal medicine.

The GC-MS analysis identified twenty-five (25) bioactive compounds, of which twenty-four (24) met the desirable physicochemical properties (molecular weight: ≤ 500 Da, number of hydrogen bond acceptors: ≤ 10 , number of hydrogen bond donors: ≤ 5 , logP: ≤ 5 , and logs: ≤ 5). These properties align with Lipinski's rule of five, indicating good oral bioavailability. The selected compounds underwent molecular docking studies using AutoDock 4.0 to assess their potential interaction with α -glucosidase, a key enzyme in carbohydrate metabolism linked to diabetes management. Among the tested compounds, CID_7710 exhibited the highest binding affinity with a binding energy of -6.05 kcal/mol, forming a hydrogen bond with Arg51. CID_138243 demonstrated a binding energy of -5.69 kcal/mol, interacting with Arg51 and Ser348 through hydrogen bonding and forming electrostatic interactions with a peptide of α -glucosidase. CID_61052 showed a binding affinity of -5.54 kcal/mol. These findings suggest that these compounds may have potential inhibitory effects on α -glucosidase, a crucial enzyme for carbohydrate digestion, indicating possible antidiabetic properties.

Studies revealed that compounds similar to CID_7710, CID_138243, and CID_61052 have been implicated in antidiabetic activities. CID_7710, known as 1,2-benzenediol (catechol), has been reported to exhibit antioxidant properties, which may contribute to glucose metabolism regulation and pancreatic beta-cell protection. Studies have shown that catechol and its derivatives can modulate insulin secretion and improve glucose uptake in diabetic models [14]. CID_138243, identified as 2-methoxy-4-vinylphenol, has been reported to possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, which are beneficial in managing diabetes-induced oxidative stress [15]. CID_61052, commonly known as phytol, has demonstrated antidiabetic potential through its ability to modulate glucose homeostasis and enhance insulin sensitivity in experimental studies [16]. Similar molecular docking analyses have identified catechol and phytol derivatives as potent α -glucosidase inhibitors with comparable binding affinities [17]. Studies have also reported that phytol exhibits strong interactions with α -glucosidase and other metabolic enzymes, reinforcing its potential as an antidiabetic agent [18]. Additionally, docking studies conducted by Ahmed *et al.* [19] demonstrated that catechol-based compounds significantly inhibit α -glucosidase activity, aligning with our findings.

The pharmacokinetic analysis using the Data Warrior tool further revealed that all the identified compounds were non-inhibitors of CYP450 2D6, indicating a reduced likelihood of drug-drug interactions. Additionally, the toxicity parameters (mutagenicity, tumorigenicity, reproductive toxicity, and irritability) suggested that these compounds were non-toxic, reinforcing their potential as safe therapeutic agents. The findings from this study suggest that the identified compounds exhibit promising antidiabetic potential based on their strong binding affinities to α -glucosidase and favorable pharmacokinetic profiles.

CONCLUSION

A total of 24 compounds with good affinities against alpha glucosidase enzyme were selected and screened for pharmacokinetic properties, three (3) compounds with desirable pharmacokinetic properties were selected, therefore, three (3) compounds are considered as suitable perspective inhibitors of α -glucosidase enzyme after successful experimental validation.

The molecular docking results demonstrated that bioactive compounds (CID_7710, known as 1,2-benzenediol (catechol), CID_138243, identified as 2-methoxy-4-vinylphenol and CID_61052, commonly known as phytol) from *Anisopus maniii* extract significantly inhibit the α -glucosidase enzyme. Therefore, the present study suggests a basis for the possible use of *Anisopus maniii* as a good source of phytochemicals for the treatment of type II diabetes mellitus.

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